

Alumni Donations and Sales of Farm Produce as Alternative Funding Strategies in Nigerian Universities

Jimoh Abiodun (Ph.D)¹& Abegunde Femi David²

¹Department of Educational Foundations,
School of General Education, Isa Kaita College of Education,
Dutsin-ma, Katsina State.

²ECWA Girls Secondary School,
Omu-Aran, Kwara State.

abiodunjimoh101@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13825863>

Abstract

The paper is on Alumni donations and sales of farm produce as alternative funding strategies in federal universities, Nigeria. The study had two objectives which are to: assess the influence of alumni donations on the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria; and to determine the influence of sales from farm produce on the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design with population of 17,919 and sample size of 398. The instrument tagged “Influence of Alumni donations and sales from farm produce on the Provision of Material Resources in Federal Universities Questionnaire (IA&SFPPMRFUQ)” was used for data collection. The validated instrument was pilot tested using Cronbach Alpha technique and a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Data collected for the study were presented in tabular form. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Findings revealed among others that the donations from alumni significantly influenced the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria, but the contributions from sales of farm produce insignificantly influenced the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria. On the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that: The management of the Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria should make deliberate efforts to coordinate alumni activities for more purposeful support from the associations since it has become obvious that government alone cannot cope with the challenges of providing and facilitating university education. Federal universities in the north central zone, Nigeria, should also engage more in farming so as to make good sales of farm produce for the provision of material resources in the study zone.

Keywords: Alumni Donations, Farm Produce, Material Resources, Federal Universities, Alternative Funding Strategies.

Introduction

The current economic situation in Nigeria underscores the fact that the government cannot exclusively finance university education. Government officials, researchers, economic analysts, and observers have conveyed this evident truth to university authorities through various means and on multiple occasions. Consequently, Onyeche (2018) has undertaken research on various

traditional methods to generate internal revenue in order to complement government grants and subsidies. Today, many Nigeria universities generate fund from alumni, sales from farm produce and many more avenues to supplement the effort of the government. This is because, among other things funds are needed for provision of material resources used in the educational process. Material resources here refers to the essential educational tools and facilities provided within schools to address the general and specific requirements of students, as well as to facilitate the teaching and learning process, both in the classroom and beyond. Therefore, material resources encompass various structures such as administrative buildings (including offices for the Vice Chancellor, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Bursar, Registrar, etc.), faculty offices, lecture halls, laboratories, storage rooms, medical facilities, records offices, school stores, libraries, music rooms, cafeterias, introductory technology labs, security posts, staff residences, school farms, as well as storage facilities. Additionally, infrastructure covers utilities like electricity, water supply, and sports fields. To guarantee the provision and upkeep of these facilities, it's essential for federal universities in the North-central Zone of Nigeria to diversify the source of their income beyond government allocations. They should explore alternative revenue strategies by generating their resources through services related means such as alumni contributions, sales from farm produce and so forth.

Concept of Alternative Funding Strategies

The other source of generating fund to manage the activities of an institution can be refers to as alternative funding strategies. Onyeché (2018) affirms that, alternative sources of income refers to individuals, organizations, locations, channels, or methods for acquiring funds that diverge from the commonly used traditional approaches for funding public university education. This encompasses deliberate strategizing and procedures designed to secure significant funds from particular individuals, groups, or activities

Material Resources in Universities

Material resources are the tangible resources that are very important for the take off and continuous operations of universities. Usman (2016), affirms that material resources are the tangible resources that can easily be seen and observed in any educational institutions such as classrooms, staff office, vehicles, health centres, libraries, laboratories, instructional facilities and so on, which directly and indirectly contributes to the achievement of educational goals and objectives. Furthermore, material resources have been recognized as highly significant elements in the educational process, and it's widely acknowledged that effective learning is impossible in the absence of essential, appropriate instructional materials. According to Maitarfsir (2003), the absence of instructional materials as teaching aids in the classroom, which are essential for enhancing a swift comprehension of the subject matter, represents a major obstacle to creating an optimal learning environment. Instructional materials encompass a range of resources, such as textbooks, educational media (including library materials in print, non-print, and electronic formats), computer software, videotapes, films, DVDs, and educational television programs. These resources serve as essential tools for schools to improve teaching, advance the acquisition of

knowledge, and offer meaningful educational experiences for both classroom groups and individual students.

Donations from Alumni

Alumni make their donations decisions based on their experience in their school. They have a clear assessment of their life in their school. When they think what they obtained in the school is more than what should be offered with their tuition, they will tend to make donations to their schools. Financial aid and scholarships are signs of good treatment from schools to students and they have positive impacts on future donations of alumni (Wang, 2018).

Farm Produce

The term farm produce, in the broadest sense, means activities aimed at the use of natural resources for human welfare, i.e., it includes all the primary activities of production (Acharya & Agarwal, 2006). But, generally, it is used to mean growing and/or raising crops and livestock. Sales connote a series of activities involved in moving the goods from the point of production to the point of consumption. It includes all the activities involved in the creation of time, place, form and possession utility. According to Thomsen (2004), the study of the sales of farm produce, comprises all the operations, and the agencies conducting them, involved in the movement of farm-produced foods, raw materials and their derivatives. This includes sales of farm produce as well as input marketing”.

Statement of the Problem

Since the right to education is one of the fundamental human rights of every citizen in Nigeria, therefore, the government at both national and sub-national levels are duty-bound to provide quality education for their citizens across all the levels of education through consistent provision of adequate fund to meet the needs of educational institutions.

It is obvious that Government makes fund available for staff recruitment and development, provision of material resources among others. Still government has not been able to meet the UNESCO 26% of Nation’s annual budget for education which had compelled Nigeria universities to embark on strikes frequently, due to insufficient material resources and many more. However, the reality of today is that government alone can no longer meet the financial demands of educational institutions as the cost of providing quality education is increasing at all levels of education and this reality has made universities to embark on alternative strategies of generating fund to complement the effort of government so that universities will not suffer unimaginable set back.

Also in response to this challenge of underfunding, many scholars have carried out a number of research on alternative funding strategies to complement funding effort of the government, for instance, Okpa (2019), Onyeche (2018), Adeniran (2017), Jimoh (2017), focused their studies on “alternative revenue for school-based funding and sustainability; alternative sources of funding and management of public university in Niger Delta; exploring innovative approach to financing functional higher education in Nigeria and impact of funding on the management of state colleges of education in northwest geo-political zone, Nigeria”.

There seems to be little or no research work “on alumni donations and sales of farm produce as alternative funding strategies in Federal Universities, Nigeria. Hence, this research work seeks to examine the “influence of alumni donations and sales from farm produce as funding alternatives strategies on the provision of material resources in Nigeria Federal Universities”.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to assess the influence of alumni donations and sales of farm produce as alternative funding strategies on the provision of material resources in federal universities in the north-central geopolitical zone, Nigeria, while the specific objectives are to:

1. find out the influence of donations from Alumni on provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria;
2. determine the influence of the sales of farm produce on the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria;

Research Questions

- i. How do the donations from Alumni influence the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria?
- ii. How do the contributions from the sales of farm produce influence the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design which seeks the views of people about a particular issue that concern them (Abdullahi, Ojulari & Jadas, 2012) was used for this study. This is also justified in the assertion of Sambo (2005) who believes that survey research can be used when the total population cannot be accessed, in such instances, information is gathered on a representative sample from which inferences are made on the whole population

The population of the study is seventeen thousand nine hundred and nineteen (17,919) which consists of six thousand and twenty-eight (6,028) teaching staff, eleven thousand eight hundred and fifty-six (11,856) non-teaching staff, and thirty-five (35) management staff. The distribution of the population of teaching, non-teaching staff and management in the federal universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria is shown in Table 1

Table 1: Population Distribution of Management, Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff, Federal Universities in North-Central Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Federal Universities in North-Central Zone	State	Teaching Staff	Non-Teaching Staff	Management Staff
1.	University of Ilorin	Kwara	1,397	2,492	05
2.	Federal University of Technology, Minna	Niger	903	1,500	05
3.	Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi	Benue	784	1,237	05
4.	University of Jos	Jos	1,621	3,100	05
5.	Federal University, Lokoja	Kogi	400	810	05
6.	Federal University, Lafia	Nasarawa	269	919	05
7.	University of Abuja	FCT	654	1,798	05
	Total	7	6,028	11,856	35

Source: Federal Universities, Northcentral Zone, Nigeria, 2022.

A sample size of three hundred and ninety-eight (398) respondents was used in the study. The sampling technique used in the study is multistage sampling technique as follows:

Stage 1 involves the selection of 4 universities. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 4 Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone which are: University of Jos, University of Abuja, University of Ilorin and Federal University Lokoja. Reason for the choice of the 4 universities is because they are similar, being conventional universities while Federal University, Minna and Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi are specialised University.

Stage 2 involves the selection of samples. The simple random sampling technique was used to select the required samples for the study. To arrive at an unbiased sample size, the study adopted the recommendation of Research Advisors (2006) sample size table (see appendix B) to select the required sample size from each of the Federal Universities in North-Central Zone. Therefore, the sample for this study consists one hundred and twenty-six (126) teaching staff, two hundred and fifty-two (252) non-teaching staff, and twenty (20) management staff, making a total of three hundred and ninety-eight (398). The sample to be used in the study is presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Sample Size for the Study

S/N	Sampled Universities	State	Sampled Teaching Staff	Sampled Non-Teaching	Sampled Mgt. Staff	Total Sample Size
1.	University of Jos	Jos	50	95	5	150
2.	University of Abuja	Abuja	20	55	5	80
3.	University of Ilorin	Kwara	43	77	5	125
4.	Federal University, Lokoja	Kogi	13	25	5	43
	Total	4	126	252	20	398

The researcher used an adapted instrument for the study titled: “Influence of Alumni donations and sales from farm produce on the Provision of Material Resources in Federal Universities Questionnaire (IA&SFPPMRFUQ)”The questionnaire was developed by B.A.Maina and adapted by the researcher to gather data from teaching and non-teaching staff of the concerned federal universities in the study area. Likert Scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) with the rating scores of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 was used respectively to rate the opinion of respondents. The instrument was divided into sections: Section “A” covers the demographic data of respondents, while Section “B” was made up of items that addressed the issues of the study.

Ndiyo (2005) opines that validation of the research instrument by is an obligation for every researcher to accomplish. Therefore the instrument for this study was tabled before an expert in the field of educational administration and planning. At the end, the researcher collected the instrument and made amendments as directed, where necessary.

Pilot study was conducted to ascertain the reliability of the research instrument. Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi which is one of the federal universities in the Zone was used for the pilot study. Twenty (20) teaching staff, twenty (20) non-teaching staff and ten (10) management staff were used for the pilot study. The information collected was analysed and were used to ascertain the reliability of the questionnaire.

Data collected from the pilot study was analysed using Cronbach Alpha technique and a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Based on the result of the pilot study, the instrument was declared reliable because the reliability coefficient falls between 0.5 and 1. This was a confirmation of test of reliability, because, according to Spiegel and Stevens in Alasoluyi (2015), an instrument is considered reliable if its reliability coefficient is between 0.5 and one (1).

The researcher employed three research assistants and organized a three day training session for them. After the training session, the questionnaire was administered to the respondents using on the spot collection technique in order to avoid loss of the questionnaire.

The research questions were analysed using frequency counts, mean, percentage, and standard deviation.

Results, Analysis and Discussion

The data generated were illustrated and presented in tables using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts ,percentage, mean and standard deviation

Table 3: Research question 1: Influence of Donations from Alumni on Provision of Material Resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria

SN	Item Statements	Respondents	A	U	D	Mean	SD
1.	More classrooms have been built as a result of donations from Alumni.	Management	14(70%)	5(25%)	1(5%)	3.800	0.767
		Teaching	79(62.7%)	10(7.9%)	37(29.4%)	3.571	1.229
		Non-Teaching	155(61.5%)	23(9.1%)	74(29.4%)	3.400	1.237
2.	Donations from alumni is used for the provision of laboratory facilities in this university.	Management	4(20%)	6(30%)	10(50%)	2.200	1.281
		Teaching	22(17.5%)	2(1.6%)	102(81%)	2.000	1.131
		Non-Teaching	38(15.1%)	2(0.8%)	212(84.1%)	2.004	1.162
3.	Donations from alumni aided provision of secure learning environment in this university.	Management	4(20%)	4(20%)	12(60%)	2.700	1.031
		Teaching	16(12.7%)	5(4%)	105(83.3%)	2.111	0.905
		Non-Teaching	45(17.9%)	9(3.6%)	198(78.6%)	2.131	1.165
4.	Donations from alumni is used to construct workshop rooms for students' learning in this university.	Management	9(45%)	5(25%)	6(30%)	3.900	1.395
		Teaching	78(61.9%)	20(15.9%)	28(22.2%)	3.333	1.186
		Non-Teaching	127(50.4%)	18(7.1%)	107(42.5%)	3.805	1.267
5.	Through the donations from alumni, generators are provided in this university.	Management	14(70%)	1(5%)	5(25%)	4.450	1.145
		Teaching	88(69.8%)	15(11.9%)	23(18.3%)	3.981	1.036
		Non-Teaching	168(66.7%)	19(7.5%)	65(85.8%)	3.349	1.242
6.	Hostel resources is provided via alumni contributions.	Management	15(75%)	3(15%)	2(10%)	3.990	1.000
		Teaching	87(69%)	15(11.9%)	24(19.1%)	4.658	1.160
		Non-Teaching	123(48.8%)	40(15.9%)	89(35.3%)	4.333	1.252
7.	Donations from alumni is used to provide fire extinguishers in this university.	Management	17(85%)	2(10%)	1(5%)	3.900	0.852
		Teaching	44(34.9%)	27(21.4%)	55(43.7%)	3.738	1.201
		Non-Teaching	158(62.7%)	51(20.2%)	43(17.1%)	3.452	1.041
8.	Through appeal fund raising from alumni, this university has been provided with borehole water.	Management	13(65%)	4(20%)	3(15%)	3.450	0.887
		Teaching	74(58.7%)	15(11.9%)	37(29.4%)	3.150	1.259
		Non-Teaching	133(52.8%)	34(13.5%)	85(33.7%)	3.035	1.354
9.	Donations from alumni is used to provide computers accessories in this university.	Management	11(55%)	1(5%)	8(40%)	3.750	1.371
		Teaching	57(45.2%)	13(10.3%)	56(44.4%)	2.952	1.337
		Non-Teaching	93(36.9%)	26(10.3%)	133(52.8%)	2.821	1.319
10.	Through alumni contribution, this university is able to construct fence in the university premises.	Management	12(60%)	4(20%)	2(20%)	3.600	1.142
		Teaching	72(57.1%)	11(8.7%)	43(34.11%)	3.182	1.405
		Non-Teaching	116(92%)	34(13.5%)	102(40.5%)	3.896	1.424

Average Response Mean = 3.35

Table 3 presents the average response mean of 3.35 which is greater than the rating mean of 3.0. Most of the items stated regarding this research question recorded a positive response and mean

that is higher than the rating mean of 3.0, which indicated strong agreement on the part of the participants. For instance, item number 6 on the table revealed that hostel resource is provided via alumni contributions. The item recorded the response means of 3.990, 4.658, and 4.333 by the management staff, teaching and non-teaching staff respectively. Details showed that 7 management staff strongly agreed with the item, 8 agreed, while 3 stayed undecided, 1 disagreed, and 1 strongly disagreed. Similarly, 40 teaching staff strongly agreed with the item, 47 agreed, 15 stayed undecided, 3 disagreed while 21 strongly disagreed. On the other hand, a total of 48 non-teaching staff strongly agreed with the item, 75 agreed, 40 stayed undecided, 71 disagreed while 18 strongly disagreed with the item. By implication, the donations from Alumni positively influenced the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: Influence of the Sales of Farm Produce on the Provision of Material Resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria

SN	Item Statements	Respondents	A	U	D	Mean	SD
1.	Fund generated from the sales of farm produce is used to provide textbooks in this university.	Management	8(40%)	10(50%)	2(10%)	2.300	0.656
		Teaching	79(62.7%)	24(19%)	23(18.3%)	3.412	0.887
		Non-Teaching	136(54%)	39(15.5%)	77(30.5%)	3.134	1.062
2.	The proceeds from the sales of farm produce in this university is used to provide science equipment.	Management	11(55%)	5(25%)	4(20%)	3.300	0.923
		Teaching	46(36.5%)	24(19%)	56(44.4%)	2.777	1.137
		Non-Teaching	101(40.1%)	54(21.4%)	97(38.5%)	2.821	1.218
3.	Through the sales of farm produce, the university is provided with stationeries for examinations.	Management	7(35%)	4(20%)	9(45%)	3.000	1.076
		Teaching	91(72.2%)	17(13.5%)	18(14.3%)	3.658	1.089
		Non-Teaching	127(50.4%)	46(18.3%)	79(31.3%)	3.134	1.152
4.	Through fund generated from the sales of farm produce, the university is provided with adequate chalkboards, chalks and dusters.	Management	14(70%)	2(10%)	4(20%)	3.450	1.099
		Teaching	46(36.5%)	11(8.7%)	69(54.8%)	2.571	1.382
		Non-Teaching	117(46.4%)	39(15.5%)	96(38.1%)	2.948	1.324
5.	Through fund generated from the sales of farm produce, the university is provided with library facilities.	Management	2(10%)	5(25%)	13(65%)	2.450	0.887
		Teaching	41(32.5%)	19(15.1%)	66(52.4%)	2.500	1.343
		Non-Teaching	108(42.9%)	47(18.7%)	97(38.5%)	2.916	1.196
6.	Fund generated from the sales of farm produce is used to provide projectors in this university.	Management	12(60%)	5(25%)	3(15%)	3.600	0.940
		Teaching	34(27%)	8(6.3%)	84(66.7%)	2.460	1.128
		Non-Teaching	119(47.2%)	44(17.5%)	89(35.3%)	3.035	1.178
7.	Fund generated from the sales of farm produce is used to provide modern teaching aids in this university.	Management	11(55%)	2(10%)	3(35%)	3.200	1.472
		Teaching	35(27.7%)	7(5.6%)	84(66.7%)	2.452	1.249
		Non-Teaching	126(50%)	56(22.2%)	70(27.7%)	3.075	1.274
8.	Through fund raised from the sales of farm produce, this university is provided with adequate chairs.	Management	9(45%)	2(10%)	9(45%)	2.850	1.725
		Teaching	66(52.4%)	24(19%)	36(28.6%)	3.087	1.145
		Non-Teaching	125(49.6%)	59(23.4%)	68(27%)	3.107	1.132
9.	Through fund generated from the sales of farm produce, this university is provided with workshops equipment.	Management	7(35%)	3(15%)	10(50%)	2.950	1.356
		Teaching	59(46.8%)	31(24.6%)	36(28.6%)	3.111	1.097
		Non-Teaching	130(51.6%)	69(27.4%)	53(21%)	3.246	1.007
10.	Through fund raised from the sales of farm produce, this university is provided with modern sick-bay.	Management	8(40%)	3(15%)	9(45%)	3.200	1.399
		Teaching	49(38.9%)	19(15.1%)	58(46%)	2.746	1.199
		Non-Teaching	114(45.2%)	58(23%)	80(31.7)	3.043	1.039

Average Response Mean = 2.98

Table 4 presents the average response mean of 2.98 which is lesser than the rating mean of 3.0. Most of the items stated regarding this research question recorded a response means lesser than

the rating mean of 3.0, which indicated disagreement on the part of the participants. Regardless, item number 3 on the table revealed that through the sales of farm produce, the university is provided with stationeries for examinations. By implication, sales of farm produce have little or no influence on the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Summary of the findings

1. In the opinions of management, teaching and non-teaching staff, the donations from Alumni significantly influence the provision of material resources, such as generators, hostel, fire extinguishers, borehole water, construction of more classrooms, etcetera, in most Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria
2. In the opinions of management, teaching and non-teaching staffs, the sales of farm produce has little or no influence on the provision of material resources, such as projectors, workshops equipment, etcetera, in most Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Discussion of the findings

Alumni significantly influence the provision of material resources, such as generators, hostel, fire extinguishers, borehole water, construction of more classrooms, etcetera, in most Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria. This finding upheld the findings of Denneen and Dretler (2012) which revealed that the alumni make donations in a way that they are able to render intellectual, physical and financial support to their alma maters. On the other hand, the research conducted by Banka (2019) revealed no significant influence of alumni contributions on the management of universities in the North Central States; specifically, in the areas of funding, infrastructural facilities, discipline, politics and quality control. However, there was a significant influence of alumni contributions in the areas of human resource management and instructional facilities.

Findings on research question two revealed that the contributions from the sales of farm produce have no significant influence on the provision of material resources in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria. Nonetheless, the respondents agreed that through the sales of farm produce, the university is provided with stationeries for examinations. The current finding is consistent with the findings of Adamu (2015) which revealed that through fund generated from the sales of farm produce, the university is provided with the spaces included classrooms, agricultural mechanics laboratories, greenhouses, land laboratories, and food processing centres as locations for students to learn, apply, and develop knowledge, attitudes, and skills.

Conclusion

Base on the findings from this study, the researcher concludes that:

1. donations from alumni is used to construct workshop rooms, laboratory facilities, borehole water, construct workshop rooms for students' learning in most Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria;

2. funds generated from the sales of farm produce is used to provide learning materials such as textbooks, stationeries for examinations, science equipment, workshops equipment, projectors and many others in Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from this studies, the followings recommendations were made:

1. Management of the Federal Universities in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria should make deliberate efforts to coordinate alumni activities for more purposeful support from the associations since it has become obvious that government alone cannot cope with the challenges of providing and facilitating university education;
2. University mangers should see the need to initiate appropriate income generating strategies such as the sales of farm produce aimed at enhancing resource mobilization in order to run their schools effectively. These income generating activities have multiplier effects in the sense that they easily assist to effectively develop infrastructure, provide research funds and on the whole affect quality delivery of the entire university system.

References

- Abduallhi, M. L., Ojulari, S. I., & Jadas, N. (2012). *Methodology in Research Report writing: A Guide to Supervisors and Students in Education, Science Technology and Engineering*. Kano: Gresleat Printers and Publishers.
- Acharya, S. S., & Agarwal, N. L. (2006). *Agricultural Marketing in India*. New Delhi: Oxford & IBH Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd.
- Adamu, T. A. (2015). *Impact of funding on quality education in Ahmadu Bello and Nasarawa Universities, Nigeria 2001-2009* (Unpublished Doctor of Philosophy Dissertation, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria–Nigeria).s
- Adeniran, O. S. (2017). Innovative approaches to financing functional higher education in Nigeria. *Josurnal of Teacher Perspective*, 12(1), 1-16.
- Alasoluyi, O. E. (2015). *Effect of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) on students' performance in Economics in Senior Secondary Schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.
- Banka, S. N. (2019). Influence of Alumni Association on the Management of Public Universities in the North Central States of Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 7(1), 31-41.
- Denneen, J., & Dretler, T. (2012). *The financially sustainable university*. Bain & Company: Americas Higher Education practice.
- Jimoh, A. (2017). *Impact of funding on the management of state colleges of education in North-west geo-political zone, Nigeria*, (Unpublished Master Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria–Nigeria).
- Maitafsir M.G. (2003). The role of English Language in students understanding and performance in Chemistry. *The Nigerian Principal Journal of ANCOPSS*, 8 (1), 49-54.
- Ndiyo, N. A. (2005). *Fundamental of Research in Behavioural Sciences and Humanities*. Calaba: Wusen Publishers Nig Ltd.
- Okpa, O. E. (2019). Exploring alternative revenue streams for school-based funding and sustainability of higher education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering Applied*

Sciences and Technology, 4(3), 259-267. Published Online, July 2019 in IJEAST (<http://www.ijeast.com>).

Onyeche, N. M. (2018). Alternative sources of funding and management of public universities in the Niger Delta States of Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 6(3), 66-73.

Research Advisors (2006). *Sample Size Table*. Retrieved 16/03/2016 from <http://www.research-advisors.com/tools/SampleSize.htm>

Sambo, A. A. (2005). *Research Method in Education*. Kano: Sterlin Horden Publishers Nigeria Limited.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), (1998). *Higher Education in Africa: Achievement, Challenges and Prospects* (UNESCO/BREDA).